

Ethnic Classification Using Support Vector Machine for Eye Color Recognition

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Abstract

An eye color detection system can provide a large amount of valuable information about a person, a classification of colors is very useful in documenting events such as pathological changes or defining how a person will respond to ocular medical defects. These classification systems range from basic light or dark descriptions of eye color to grading and employing photographic standards of the static profile from a real-time video capture. This paper adopted the use of a Support Vector Machine (SVM) a procedure that uses a non-separable dataset from the eye authentication matrix, based on the model's complexity that doesn't allow for a separating hyperplane axis. The SVM uses a soft margin, a hyperplane that separates many, but not all data points from the input matrix and makes classification based on five different eye color. The model was tested on the dataset on different epochs and the best fit is discussed in the result section.

Keywords: Eye color recognition, Support Vector Machine, Model complexity, Photographic imagery, Model classification, Color Analytics.

1 Introduction

The eye color in humans is regulated differently [11, 31, 7, 8, 13, 3], i.e. instead of blue as in most human beings, an autosomal recessive eye in a species such as corucia zebra is classified as black and the autosomal dominant color is termed yellow-green. Most color classification systems are trained to learn this process of color identification and many adopt standard procedures. As the length of perception of color depends on viewing conditions, the

amount and kind of illumination in the hue of the surrounding environment helps to explain the perception of eye color. Most eye colors in adults can usually be detected between three to six months of age and sometimes later in life. Trying to observe the iris of an infant from the side profile using only transmitted light with no reflection from the iris can accurately detect the presence and absence of a few levels of melanin in the eye. Certain changes in

lightening and darkening of the eye color in puberty sometimes give the wrong classification of eye color in terms of accuracy in detection. Other complex attributes in eye color detection lie in the study of a set of Caucasian twins where both fraternal and identical attributes show that eye color over time can be subject to change and demelanisation of the iris can be genetically proven. Most of the eye color changes have been observed to be Caucasian ethnicity with hazel and amber hue. There is color disagreement between certain objects between two people, this causes a discrepancy in the presence of melanin in the iris, which is the main factor in detecting eye color. The higher the rate of melanin in the iris of the eyes, the denser the texture of the melanin, and the darker the color of a person's pupil, and this could be also a result of environmental ethnicity.

A person's eye contains two different types of light and color receptors in the retina of the eyes and is depicted in different colors like green, black, blue, red, and hazel. These are basic color classifications of the eyes used in this paper. A person exposed to light has his/her eye color hit by a part of the back of the eye which is often called the 'yellow spot'. Most soft biometric models have shown their utility in color classification models by reducing the search space insignificant measures. This mostly leads to improved recognition performance reduction in computation time and speed of the process. Most of these common soft biometrics are models that are ethnicity-based on gender, hair color, iris color, and gender matching. The proceeding section discusses methods for performing ethnicity classification on iris images.

2 Literature Review

Current research [3, 24, 29, 5, 14, 32, 4, 20] focuses on performing ethnicity and gender classification on iris images that present a novel supervised auto-encoder which is based on an approach of Deep Class-Encoder. This process uses classes of labels to learn discriminative representation for a given sample by directly mapping the learned feature vector to its label. The proposed model was evaluated on two different datasets each for ethnicity and gender classification. The results obtained in their search showed that the effectiveness in comparison to the existing approaches and state-of-the-art methods is highly significant [9, 6, 25, 18].

The biometric traits in eye color detection are both physical and behavioural in terms of characteristics and attributes that can be extracted from the human body that would help differentiate individuals from one another. These tools often lack information that is permanent and are insufficient in discriminative to the unique identification of an individual. These traits are most valuable since they help in the recognition and enhancement of the performance of the automated biometric systems [12, 23, 22, 1, 21, 2, 17, 30]; they reduce the search space

and enhance accuracy in mapping for a perfect match. One of the most common biometric modalities is ethnicity and eye color detection which extracts features from the face and iris.

The iris texture has emerged as the most robust and widely used biometric measure for automated identity detection in most studies and has also been established as having a presence of similarity information in iris patterns for most people who discriminate between ethnicity and gender. Lagree and Bowyer [15, 27, 28, 19] in their work extend the process by computing texture features of a variety of horizontal and vertical bands of normalised iris images. Features that were adopted were 620 from a total of fourteen regions in a given database of images. This set of features was used as input to a sequential minimum optimisation algorithm for classification. A similar set of extracted features was used to perform ethnicity classification of iris images and concatenated histograms were used to perform gender classification on iris images on an in-house dataset [26, 10, 16]. However, the work described in this paper uses a singular image front-end was used for input classification the main contribution is classifying the color based on the nature and texture of the eyes, this is discussed in the proceeding section.

Figure 1: A model framework for eye color recognition for an input image based on SVM as the inference engine.

3 Method

The method adopted here is based on image capture of 60 participants from a mobile camera lens which is stored in an online data storage system together with their demographic information, this is to be assessed in a workstation during analysis. The datasets are divided into training and test sets and the SVM is for feature extraction and classification of the right eye for the matrix which was generated from each input image. The best match from the database for an input image is based on a computational SVM (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Image capture of 60 participants from a mobile camera lens which is stored in an online data storage system.

The procedure uses a non-separable dataset from the eye authentication matrix, based on the model's complexity this might not allow for a separating hyperplane axis. In such a case, the SVM uses a soft margin, a hyperplane that separates many, but not all data points from the input matrix. Therefore, two standard formulations for data classification involve adding slack variables s_i and a penalty parameter C . The L^1 -norm problem is:

$$\min_{w,b,s} \left(\frac{1}{2}(W, W) + c \sum_i s_i \right) \text{ such that, } \quad (1)$$

$$y_i(\langle w, x_i \rangle) \geq 1 - s_i, s_i \geq 0$$

The L^1 -norm refers to using s_i as slack variables instead of their squares. The three-solver equation for SVM fit minimizes the L^1 -norm problem. The L^2 -norm problem is:

$$\min_{w,b,s} \left(\frac{1}{2}(W, W) + c \sum_i s_i^2 \right)$$

$$\min_{w,b,s} \left(\frac{1}{2}(W, W) + c \sum_i s_i \right) - \sum_i \alpha_i (y_i(\langle w, x_i \rangle + b) - (1 - s_i)) - \sum_i \mu_i s_i$$

$$b = \sum_i \alpha_i y_i x_i$$

$$\sum_i \alpha_i y_i = 0$$

$$\alpha = C - \mu_i$$

$$\alpha_i y_i x_i \geq 0$$

$$\max_{\alpha} \sum_i \alpha_i - \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sum_j i \alpha_j x_i y_j \langle x_i x_j \rangle \quad (2)$$

subject to the constraints $\sum_i y_i \alpha_i$ and $0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C$. The final set of inequalities, $0 \leq \alpha_i \leq C$, indicates the constant C is called a box constraint. C keeps the allowable values of the Lagrange multipliers α_i in a "box", a bounded region.

The gradient equation for b gives the solution b in terms of the set of nonzero α_i , which correspond to the support vectors. This process is adopted for all input images and the best match is also determined using the predictive concept of the model. Since all information is collected that includes the participant's demography

each best match also produces basic information about the participant's attributes. The proceeding section discusses some of the results obtained from the analysis.

4 Result

Figure 3 shows a window output for a detected image match from the list of information, this information is obtained only when the best match is detected. An accuracy and error test is also conducted for each image match. The first module connects the profile of the face to the camera where both eyes are directed to the left facing the camera. A static image of the profile is captured and used as input. Every input profile follows the same procedure. The module is where the eye color is detected, this follows a computational step that classifies the eye color based on five different color metrics such as 'black', 'blue', 'brown', 'green' and 'hazel'. Java was used for image processing and classification based on the eye module. The print command helps to aggregate the resultant output of the best match and produce input formation that relates to the input image given online. The best match is most important in pattern recognition and hence the tracker operating characteristics (TOC) are computerised for every input image of the SVM on different epochs in dB aggregate of all 60 images. The dataset was for four different sets, two from the test set and two from the training set, the main rationale is to set a fast-processing speed and at the same time an accurate match.

The different epochs depend on the nature of the search, e.g, if a match produces a false detection noted by the mismatch in eye color, a different epoch is set between 2–11 dB . Figure 4 below shows the result for different SVM models. Two of its epoch have a high rate of performance between 0.9 and 1.0% with the least error at 0.01% at 10.4 and 9 dB in the first quartile. The tracking is based on a sum of the difference in monopulse for the SVM to estimate the direction with the dataset of images, the tracker obtains the difference in each vector matrix that makes up the given set by phase reversing half of the sum of a steering vector of the matrix. The second quartile has a performance rate of 0.98 and 1.0% with a minimal error of 0.003% at 9.4 and 7.4 dB epochs in the first set. The probability of target track detection for a single target with and without the presence of false alarms is applicable for a dataset matrix with five groups of attributes of eye color, this is adopted given that the supervised learning can be adapted and the learning process is induced. The highest probability detected for the fourth quartile at 6.4 and 3.9 dB has a performance rate of 0.98 and 1.0% with a minimal error of 0.001%. This is also seen in the fourth quartile. The probability computation is set for a false track due to false alarms in the neighborhood of a single target for each vector matrix that makes up the whole set.

Figure 3: Window output of detection image for eye color search in the list of information from the online database.

5 Conclusion

This paper investigated eye color recognition for ethnic classification using a support vector machine for a mobile-based app. The method is implemented using SVM on different epochs on the datasets. A set of front profile images of people with different eye colors were collected at the initial stage from different regions online and offline, using the camera lens of a mobile phone, some local data were collected including online images; these are stored online. Each image is then randomly selected as input for a perfect match and its correlating demographic information is produced when the best fit is found. Error and performance test was conducted for all input images for four different quartiles for the set. Different epoch was set for the SVM to determine the fastest processing speed to be adopted for each eye color recognition on a selected epoch. The plan for this tool is to set a parallel processing image recognition speed for more than one input image and set the detection speed to a minimum frequency with high bandwidth.

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(a) TOC for four different epochs for the first quarter of the image set.

(b) TOC for four different epochs for the second quarter of the image set.

Figure 4: TOC for both the first and second quarter of input images in the online storage database

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(a) TOC for four different epochs for the third quarter of the image set.

(b) TOC for four different epochs for the fourth quarter of the image set.

Figure 5: TOC for both the third and fourth of all images used in the study.

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